

RULES OF ENGLISH SPEECH CULTURE

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Annotation: The article shows that the education of a comprehensively developed person is a priority of the education system of the country and the growing attention to the study and teaching of foreign languages in the country. To teach that it is not possible to master the English language at a high level without following the rules of English speech culture and strictly following the existing rules in this area.

Keywords: upbringing of a harmoniously developed person, foreign language, speech culture, rules, communication, communication.

One of the pedagogical sources defines the concept of "speech culture" as follows: the degree of mastery of the skills of logical, accurately figurative, clear and expressive delivery of ideas through speech. It is obvious that in this definition, the concept of "speech culture" is interpreted as one of the characteristics of the individual, and its essence is correctly explained.

Speech culture has both general and specific aspects in terms of existing languages and national cultures on Earth. Its general features are characterized by speech formation, participation of speech organs in expression, interpersonal communication, verbal (verbal), nonverbal (non-verbal, written), information exchange, emotional-volitional influence, etc. Specific aspects of speech serve to highlight the unique features of each language or national culture, such as structural, logical, volitional, communicative, productive. Accordingly, in the process of organizing communication in different languages, it is advisable to follow the rules of speech culture, taking into account the general and specific aspects of speech. In particular, the rules of speech culture, taking into account the general and specific aspects of speech in English, which is recognized as the leading language in the relations between the peoples of the world, ensure the effective exchange of personal information. In other words, it is impossible to master the English language at a high level without following the rules of speech culture and strictly following the existing rules in this area.

What speech rules, requirements should be followed in English-based communication?

The culture of speech in English-based communication has its own ancient and authoritarian traditions. In the process of communication, the rules of speech, reading from the requirements, non-compliance with them are a sign of uncivilization and rudeness. Therefore, any person, even if he is able to communicate fluently in English, but does not follow the rules and requirements of speech, or does not want to obey them, of course, he will not achieve anything. In order to achieve the expected result of the dialogue, representatives of other nationalities must be sufficiently aware of the rules of speech, requirements for addressing, greeting, saying goodbye, thanking, apologizing, congratulating, etc. in English to acquaintances and strangers. For example, in English, there is no officially recognized limit to the use of you and you forms of communication. Both forms of the address (you and you) are represented by a single you pronoun.

The pronoun You is used in all formal and informal communication on the basis of expressiveness, selection and construction of relevant words and phrases.

According to the culture of speech, the rules of etiquette (etiquette) recognized by the nation speaking the relevant language should also be taken into account. In particular, the use of the pronouns you and you in the Uzbek language takes into account the social status of the interlocutor, the nature of interpersonal relations, the situation of communication, both formal and informal. In Uzbek communication, addressing you is usually applied to children, relatives, children of acquaintances, and sometimes to students.

The rules of etiquette (etiquette) in interpersonal communication, based on the essence of speech, firstly, provide speech politeness, and secondly, increase the effectiveness of speech. Therefore, in teaching students to communicate in English, it is necessary to teach them not only grammatically, syntactically and morphologically correct, clear and understandable expression, but also to ensure that it is polite and pleasant. purposeful.

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At the same time, as in all languages, in English-based communication, addressing the interlocutor by name gives him the opportunity to achieve the expected result of the dialogue. So, the most characteristic feature of communication in English is politeness and, from time to time, recognition of the identity of the interlocutor. For example, this can be seen in the following timeframe questions:

Example 1. A complete stranger is politely addressed as follows: - Excuse me, could you tell me the time, please? (Excuse me, can you please tell me what time it is?)

Example 2 The acquaintance is politely addressed as follows: - What time is it, Tom? (Tom, what time is it now?)

"What time is it?" The interrogation is usually used in the family in the company of relatives, friends and acquaintances and is expressed in a polite manner. However, addressing a stranger with this request is not considered polite, on the contrary, it is considered rude. Instead, "Excuse me, could you tell me the time, please?" The use of the request in the family, relatives, friends and acquaintances indicates that the request is insincere or artificial.

Thus, in the process of learning English, students should be aware of the factors that ensure that the speech, which is the basis for communication in this language, acquires a cultural character and is organized in accordance with the rules of etiquette. Following the rules of speech culture, as in all languages, ensures that communication in English is based on politeness and sincerity. This ensures that the dialogue is "live" and the expected result is achieved.

List of used literature:

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